

Patriarchy and Femme Fatale in Wole Soyinka's *Death and the King's Horseman* and William Shakespeare's *Othello*

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Abstract

Femme fatale is a negative label embedded in gender norms and usually ascribed to alluringly beautiful women who are often considered dangerous and destructive. This paper explores patriarchy and femme fatale in Wole Soyinka's *Death and the King's Horseman* and William Shakespeare's *Othello*. Through a comparative analysis, the study examines how the two texts depict gender dynamics, power structure, as well as the consequences of societal expectations on women. It seeks to show through its adoption of the concepts of patriarchy and sexism, that femme fatale is a narrative of men and that the women often referred to as femme fatales are victims of a patriarchal system that blames beautiful women for the tragedy of men while exonerating the men from their freedom to make choices and take responsibility for the consequences of their actions. The study establishes that, the dilemma of the central female characters in the two texts under study exposes the extreme and peculiar expression of patriarchy which is tragically self-destructive. The methodological approach adopted in this study is purely qualitative. The study reveals that, in the societies of the texts under study, the cultural norms and mores conspire to keep women in their place in the scheme of things, and, of course, it is a scheme that is hierarchical and patriarchal. The study recommends that literatures should extol the virtues of women's beauty as against the destructive tendencies usually associated with them as adumbrated by the concept of femme fatale.

Keywords: Femme fatale, Patriarchy, Shakespeare, Society, Soyinka

Introduction

This paper critically investigates patriarchy and femme fatale in William Shakespeare's *Othello* and Wole Soyinka's *Death and the King's Horseman* from a comparative prism. It is premised on the assumption that some women are dangerous and destructive by virtue of their alluring and irresistible beauty and the reason they are labelled "femme fatales". The assumption is supported by tales from various cultures which demonstrate femme fatale motif. In like manner, writers like Shakespeare and Soyinka exploit the same motif as they create formal dramatic works (plays). The study is interested in the points of convergences and divergences in Shakespeare and Soyinka's appropriation of the femme fatale myth. The interest of these writers in the myth surrounding femme fatale as they utilise it as part of the organising principle of their discourse on male-female relationships, makes it worthy of being explored in an academic study.

Femme fatale is a resolute and indefatigable woman who is both alluring and irresistible just as she is regarded as highly dangerous. Although it is a French term for a deadly woman, it has been literally translated as “fatal woman”. Femme fatale is also regarded as a classic and extremely captivating character known to exist in the culture, folklore and myth of many cultures and found in several sources of the mythology and literature of various origins and eras. In other words, throughout history, the femme fatale, which is present in so many different forms, is also found almost in every society or culture. In fact, in mythology and other folkloric expressions, literature, visual arts and the cinema, femme fatale is known to be a destructive cauldron. That is, a woman who is irresistibly beautiful and alluring, with the capacity for enchanting men, ultimately destroys them. It therefore buttresses the fact that femme fatales have been present right from the foundation of the world. Consequently, the concept of femme fatale has been a recurrent theme in literature, the visual arts, and the cinema, and this suggests that it has a special social and psychological significance that makes it worthy of identification and analysis (Glenn Wilson 28).

The term patriarchy has been defined as a system of male authority which oppresses women through its social, political and economic institutions. Feminist theorists have argued that in any of the historical forms that patriarchal society takes, whether it is feudal, capitalist or socialist, a sex gender system and a system of economic discrimination operate simultaneously. They characterise patriarchy as an unjust social system that is oppressive to women (Godiya Allanana Makama 117). Originally used to describe the power of the father as head of a household, the term patriarchy has been used within post 1960s feminism to refer to the systematic organisation of male supremacy and female subordination (Makama 117). Patriarchy can also be seen in the light of a social relation with a demarcation between men and women, which enables the men to dominate women. The domination gives the male gender an overriding dominance over the female gender. The control is maintained by excluding women from access to necessary economically productive resources and by restricting women’s sexuality (2).

Essentially, both Western and African societies under study are patriarchal in nature. Consequently, they have become systems of social stratification and differentiation on the basis of sex, which provides material advantages to males while simultaneously placing severe constraints on the roles and activities of females (Makama 116). According to him, Okpe sees patriarchy as a

broad network or system of hierarchical organisation that cuts across political, economic, social, religious, cultural, industrial and financial spheres under which the overwhelming number of upper positions in society are occupied or controlled and dominated by men (2). Thus, any system that operationalises an order that accords men undue advantage over women is considered patriarchal (Makama 117).

The masculine traditional canon has always dominated both the Western (mine) and African consciousness concerning beliefs and existence. The culture, the tradition, the languages, the names, the types of vocation, even the biological and physiological structure of humans as determined by this environment and nature, have always reemphasised the dominance of the male. Man grew with such... the female counterpart was made to accept it as the only way... woman was indeed a stereotype, a symbol of life, cocooned by cultural beliefs (John Yeseibo 80).

The excerpt above is Ahmed Yerima's view of the supercilious nature of patriarchal societies and their subjugation and stereotyping of women as noted by Yeseibo. Essentially, it reveals that, patriarchal societies deal with a variety of attitudes and customs found not only in both Western and African societies but also in very different people. It also points to the fact that, the debased image of some beautiful and attractive women as femme fatales and their negative portrayal in literary works, with particular reference to the selected texts, is a vivid and accurate reflection of the dominant patriarchal nature of both Western and African societies. Studies have also shown that the stereotype of femme fatale image/character has long been established by patriarchal societies. Thus, mythology, folklore, religion, literature and the cinema all highlight various instances of the representations and interpretations of beautiful and irresistible women as femme fatales.

Literature Review

Femme fatale has been imagined in several ways in different cultural contexts and historical eras, starting from Eve, Medusa, the Sirens, and Helen of Troy as mythical women even through historical figures like Mata Hari, as well as historical figures from the Classical period like Cleopatra, Clytemnestra, and Messalina, to purportedly seductive and enchanting women in contemporary society such as Winnie Mandela, Ini Edo, Destiny Etiko to mention but a few. Being

a famously symbolic figure, femme fatale has been in existence in one form or another in virtually all cultures throughout history. For Tugce Ozdinc, the femme fatale archetype that exists since the creation of the universe is closely linked with evil by the patriarchal discourse (175).

Ruth Markus argues that femme fatale has appeared throughout history in the form of different women and given names originated in assorted Biblical stories, various mythologies, literature and poetry (187). Ngugi wa Thiong'o asserts that the heart is hungry only for what it has chosen (23), and he who loves beauty does not complain while he is pursuing it (164). This corroborates James Maxfield's argument that attraction to a woman threatens men's ability to adhere to the code; it calls forth tender emotions that undermine toughness (4). Thus, men's real threat as observed by Maxfield, is not just beauty but the emotional dependency they feel towards the object of their admiration and attraction (Maxfield 14). Ngugi's assertion is sustained by Maxfield, who posits that femme fatale is typically conceived of as an extremely beautiful and attractive woman who deliberately tries to lead men to their destruction; she is composed of equal parts of seductive beauty and cunning (1).

However, this lopsided view of femme fatale reduces captivating women to evil and destructive beings. This is very significant and typical of most discourses on femme fatale. It is worthy of note that most discourses on femme fatale are always hinged on the assumption that entrancingly beautiful women are seductresses, whores, temptresses and wicked destroyers. And, of course, this kind of discourse is built on the assumed destructive beauty of alluring women. Patrick Bade states that femme fatale is an enchantress, a destroyer, priestess, siren, sphinx and an angel of death... Death and eroticism surround her, and her cruelty grows in intensity as the male tries to escape her clutches, for she is malignant, threatening, destructive, and fascinating (8-9).

Bade's assertion seems to be men's attempt to cope with the confusion and frustration experienced by the struggle with their desperate inner cravings for pleasure and satisfaction amid social conformity, and their inability to make sense out of the tragedy and absurdity of life, especially, in the face of the object of beauty, admiration and attraction. Nevertheless, for Angela Carter, the prevailing notion of femme fatale is one-dimensional and criticises a society that paints women only as passive instruments of vice, thereby failing to see beyond the stereotype (249). This study aligns with Carter's argument to demystify the concept of femme fatale by bringing to

the fore the fact that, a beautiful woman cannot destroy a man without his contributing actions. To this end, my stake is that the concept of femme fatale is a patriarchal stereotyped narrative that does not consider the roles men play in their relationships with the women regarded as femme fatales that lead to their tragedy.

For Rebecca Stott, the femme fatale can be a prostitute, man-haunting aristocrat, vampire, an African queen, native (black) woman or murderess, and she also crosses boundaries of class and race (8). In addition, Mario Praz cites Moreau's own statement on woman as "Fatality...Evil and Death" (309). On the contrary, in refutation of the unfair characterisation and stigmatisation of beautiful women as femme fatales, Carter lifts the veil of these purported monstrous women and shows that this myth is another "consolatory device" freeing men from the burden of controlling their desires (5).

Patriarchy

A fundamental concept in feminism is patriarchy. M. H. Abrams asserts that patriarchy is male privilege and domination over women (146). In the same vein, Kate Millett opines that patriarchal powers still have the military and financial means. Thus, for her, patriarchy is not only male domination of females but also a militaristic hierarchy among males (xii). This is sustained by bell hooks who notes that patriarchy is a system of domination that has become institutionalised, and it is perpetuated and maintained (*Feminism is for Everybody* 7). hooks' view is reiterated by Ngozi Ezenwa-Ohaeto who argues that patriarchy is a system that extols male authority, domination and supremacy over the female in all spheres of human endeavour. Its tenets have remained unprinted but have been actively governing people's lives and transactions over decades (59).

Synopsis of *Death and the King's Horseman*

Soyinka's *Death and the King's Horseman* is a play which tells the story of the struggles, difficulties and obstacles experienced by Elesin Oba, the King's Horseman, on the night he is expected to commit ritual suicide in order to accompany the late king into the afterlife. In *Death and the King's Horseman*, Elesin Oba is the King's horseman who has a good reputation for bravery, honour and wisdom. His pride and primary responsibility is to accompany the deceased king into the afterlife or the "abode of the gods" as tradition demands. However, Elesin, despite

his numerous wives, fails in his central mission because of his desperate inner cravings for the gratification of his amorous desire for a beautiful young girl betrothed to another man, Iyaloja's son, in tandem with men's quest for the pleasure principle. Consequently, Olunde, his son, dies in his place to salvage his family's heritage and reputation from the reproach and ridicule that his father's failure to execute the sacred obligation will bring on them.

Synopsis of *Othello*

Shakespeare's *Othello* also known as "The Tragedy of Othello, the Moor of Venice" is regarded as the greatest study of jealousy and envy ever written. It depicts a profound love ruined by jealousy. The play exposes the private life of a man of great stature destroyed by his ignorance and personal flaws. To this end, it is known to be Shakespeare's only domestic tragedy. The play tells the story of Othello, a valiant general, a man of royal descent, and the governor of Cyprus at one time. He is esteemed by the Venetian senate, which calls for his military leadership when the state is threatened by Islamic aggression. However, at the start of the play, attention is diverted from Othello's duties and accomplishments to his emotional response to family crisis.

Othello's weakness is his predisposition towards jealousy, and, of course, it is a failing aroused in him by the malevolent villain, Iago. The malignant and cunning Iago makes Othello extremely jealous and mad. He orchestrates situations that make the Moor to believe that his wife has an illegal affair with Cassio. Othello's gullibility and naivety make him unable to detect Iago's intrigues and manipulations. He suspects his wife but keeps trusting Iago and, this, eventually, leads to his downfall. Being malevolent, Iago takes advantage of Othello's vulnerabilities and exploits his trust and dependence on him as an "honest" person.

It is pertinent to state that, the similarities and differences in the representations and interpretations of femme fatale in both Western and African societies as reflected in the selected plays show that, nearly every culture explores similar themes even though writers from different cultures may develop the themes differently as done by Shakespeare and Soyinka. Thus, the study argues that the beautiful and captivating women who are labelled, represented and interpreted as femme fatales are cultural productions of Western and African societies; irrespective of their different historical and geographical settings. The playwrights' gender and their patriarchal ideology influence their depiction of beautiful and alluring women as femme fatales as illustrated

in the lives of the major female characters under study. Their beauty is considered a threat and danger to men and the reason they are vilified as seductresses, whores, sirens, vampires, witches, manipulators to mention but a few.

Arguably, femme fatale is culturally constructed because it is a negative label ascribed to beautiful women according to cultural norms, values and beliefs. Also, though the image of femme fatale is so deeply entrenched in the psyche of the society that beautiful and alluring women are stereotyped and misrepresented, it is mythical in nature thereby validating the myths and beliefs of both Western and African patriarchal societies. Shakespeare and Soyinka's construction of beautiful women as femme fatales in the texts under study draws attention to the similarities in cultures of Europe and Africa and thus reflects the inherited traditions, warped perceptions and prejudices of their patriarchal societies. In *Othello* and *Death and the King's Horseman*, women are not only constructed as naturally changeable and deceptive but also as property, the ownership of which reflects on a man's power and superiority.

Pragati Das avers that certainly Desdemona's very much feminised qualities of passivity, softness and obedience are no match for Othello's masculine qualities of dominance, aggression and authority. After Othello in his jealousy has struck Desdemona and spoken harshly to her, she tells Iago, "I am a child to chiding". Protected by a system which makes women the weaker, dependent sex, Desdemona is unequipped to deal with such aggression; she is helpless against Othello. Desdemona thus retreats into childlike behaviour to escape from reality (40) of the power of patriarchal culture that holds women captive. Desdemona obeys Othello's every command so as not to displease him. Nevertheless, Othello denies her right to a voice and her identity diminishes until she fits into the stereotype of the silent woman just like the beautiful damsel in *Death and the King's Horseman*.

Significantly, Shakespeare and Soyinka represent two distinct cultural milieus. Thus, while Shakespeare is representative of Europe in the Elizabethan period, where beauty and love were significant social considerations, Soyinka, on the other hand, is representative of Contemporary Africa's apprehension of the same. However, while in the Renaissance period the femme fatale myth was accepted because women lived in a male-ordered society, the 21st Century African idea of the myth differs remarkably due to the feminist movement and globalisation. Writers,

particularly feminists, have rejected the idea of portraying beautiful women as intrinsically destructive by considering human actions and personal choices in the causality of tragedies, especially in a romantic relationship.

Quite obviously, despite the fact that the two periods are different, that is, Renaissance and Contemporary Africa-20th/21st Century, historically and culturally, the idea of femme fatale is the same across both cultures as vividly portrayed in the selected texts. The dilemma of the central female characters in the texts under study exposes the extreme and peculiar expression of patriarchy which is tragically self-destructive. In fact, patriarchal constructs place the woman in the position of stereotyping, oppression, exploitation, stigmatisation, misinterpretations and misrepresentations, for which cause she is regarded as a beast of burden and a tool basically meant for the gratification of the caprices of men and manhood.

In the societies of the texts under investigation, the cultural norms and mores conspire to keep women in their place in the scheme of things, and, of course, it is a scheme that is hierarchical and patriarchal. Thus, they are not expected to argue or disagree with men. This is seen playing out in the lives of the major female characters-Elesin's (unnamed) bride (*Death and the King's Horseman*) and Desdemona (*Othello*). It is even grossly unacceptable for women to present views on society different from men. Yerima's explanation of the supercilious nature of patriarchy and its stereotyping, subjugation, and oppression of women corroborates Simone de Beauvoir's argument that femme fatale myth is the myth that holds women responsible for the sins of the flesh and for tempting men, revealing that the purpose of the myth is to represent women according to patriarchy's needs, and in contradistinction to whatever man considers himself to be (Elizabeth Fallaize 90).

It will therefore not be out of place to say that the representations of beautiful women as femme fatales is society's vilification of women to accommodate patriarchal needs. Nneka Ibeli notes that the image of women presented in the works of some male playwrights has largely demonstrated the image of the patriarchal order and consistently given negative images of women (230). Ibeli explains that in *Death and the King's Horseman*, the nameless young maiden is seen as a fluff by Elesin Oba. Elesin, seeing his downfall, blamed the young maiden for his misfortune. Though Elesin is aware of the fact that he neglected the advice of the powerful woman, Iyaloja,

and chose to toy with his people's tradition, he still found it expedient to blame the woman (230) as the reason for his downfall.

It is noteworthy that femme fatale is a patriarchal construction of both Western and African societies that assigns negative roles to women on account of their gender. The construction, representations and interpretations of beautiful women as femme fatales vividly reflect the patriarchal image of beautiful women in general. Adeighon Idemudia-Uwadinma, while commenting on Wole Soyinka's *Kongi's Harvest* and *A Dance of the Forests* avers that even though there are prominent female characters that are portrayed even stronger than some male characters, there seems to be a conscious effort by Soyinka to portray these women though as strong characters but in roles that are more derogatory than popular (3).

In both societies of the plays, the central male characters' patriarchal idiosyncrasies of male domination, power and freedom pave the way for their actions and personal choices as portrayed in the texts under study, and, this, of course, lead to their tragedy. For instance, in *Death and the King's Horseman*, Elesin Oba, despite his numerous wives, fails in his central mission because of his desperate inner cravings for the gratification of his amorous desire for a beautiful young girl betrothed to another man, Iyaloja's son in tandem with men's quest for the pleasure principle. Elesin's attention gets fatally diverted when he rivets his eyes on a ravishingly beautiful damsel and chooses to have his way with her. Elesin Oba's tragic flaw is the lust and greed residing in his nature and it leads to his tragedy.

In fact, the tragedy of Elesin Oba is the societal construction of excessive rights, especially in terms of getting whatever he wants, including women. In a demonstration of male superiority, Elesin also tells Jane Pilkings to shut up... "You are the wife of the District Officer... That is my wife sitting down there. You notice how still and silent she sits? My business is with your husband (66). In *Othello*, patriarchal domination of women by men causes Othello not to listen to Desdemona. His lack of communication with his wife deprives him of the necessary information that would have averted the calamity he plunges into. He takes Desdemona for a whore whose body and beauty blindfolds and ensnares him (IV. i. 206–208), and he refuses to let go of the notion of her infidelity. Consequently, he abuses her slanderously on so many occasions and calls her "a

devil” (IV. i. 240), “a subtle whore” (IV. ii. 21), “strumpet” (IV. ii. 81), “a cunning whore of Venice” (IV. ii. 89).

Femme fatale connotes the same meaning across all cultures in both Western and African societies. Consequently, both Western and African playwrights have persistently, obsessively, and viscerally dramatised the alluring beauty of some women as evil, dangerous, and destructive. Their assumed capability to lure men/lovers to their inescapable destruction by charming and intoxicating them with their beauty and love is a patriarchal stereotype. Thus, they are portrayed as unusual women with irresistible beauty and power to corrupt, distract, and even destroy men as illustrated in the lives of Desdemona and Elesin’s (unnamed) bride. For instance, in *Othello*, Desdemona is portrayed as a femme fatale, whose beauty enthralls Othello so much that it changes his course of action. Her beauty is such that according to Cassio, poets are not able to describe it (II. i. 61–65).

Desdemona is also portrayed as a temptress because Othello gets so engrossed in her beauty that he persuades her to elope with him. Also, in his pursuit of Desdemona’s beauty, he marries her against her father’s wishes. Thus, Cassio jokingly says of her: “She that I spake of, our great captain’s captain” (II. i. 74). The female characters in the literary texts are bound by societal/cultural norms with little or no freedom of expressing their personal opinions. This clearly manifests in the lives of the major female characters—Elesin Oba’s (unnamed) bride in *Death and the King’s Horseman* and Desdemona and Emilia in *Othello*. The literary texts reveal how women are not allowed to have freedom. Instead, they are made to adhere to strict social hierarchies and stringent rules about women’s conduct and behaviour both in public and in the home. In other words, women’s lives, rights and freedom are severely circumscribed by patriarchy while men are allowed to enjoy the privileges of long years of tradition to dominant and superior roles in all aspects of life.

In *Othello*, Emilia decries the unfair and biased rules that are only applicable to women while the men are excluded from such (IV. iii. 95-99). Emilia does not see any genuine reason why women should be treated differently from men. She goes further to say: ‘The ills they do/ their ills instruct us so’ (IV. iii. 106). Moreover, a critical perusal of *Othello* also reveals that the strict adherence to patriarchal laws, rules and stereotypes is responsible for the play’s tragedy (Das 39).

The female characters in the texts are made to submit to the patriarchal order of the society and they are not permitted to rebel against patriarchy. According to Das, Gayle Greene summarises this position in her claim that the tragedy of *Othello* stems from “men’s misunderstanding of women and women’s inability to challenge and protect themselves from society’s conception of them” (39–40) as wicked temptresses, whores, femme fatales, deceivers, evil, manipulators to mention but a few as manifested in Desdemona, Emilia, Elsin’s bride and Bianca.

Das further notes that in *Othello*’s blunt refusal to hear Desdemona’s own protestations of innocence, *Othello* is very much a tragedy in which the female is subordinated by the male (40). Desdemona, the beautiful and charming daughter of the Venetian Senator, is also depicted as passive and obedient. She is expected to live according to the dictates of patriarchy as represented by her father. She is to accept her father’s choice of a husband without any objection. Consequently, Brabantio finds it difficult and unimaginable that his daughter, properly brought up in Venetian customs and traditions can love and willingly elope with *Othello*, the Moor. Brabantio has always regarded Desdemona as the typical “chaste, silent, obedient” daughter that is greatly admired and valued by the Venetian society. He thus declares, “A maiden never bold,/ Of spirit so still and quiet that her motion/ Blushed at herself; and she, in spite of nature,/... To fall in love with what she feared to look on!...” (I. iii. 94-106). The plight of the central female characters in the two plays—*Othello* and *Death and the King’s Horseman* is that they have been brainwashed and trained to have a delicate and submissive attitude towards their male counterparts, whether they be fathers or husbands. They are to be “angels” in the homes. Thus, in *Othello*, when Desdemona conducted herself as a young patriarchal/Venetian woman, her father referred to her as a “gentle mistress and a “jewel” (I. iii. 176,193).

Conclusion

Femme fatale is a patriarchal construct which, like other deliberately contrived social/cultural constructs, serves as a medium for the explanation of the eventual tragedy of men as depicted in the selected texts. This study corroborates Simone de Beauvoir’s argument that, the femme fatale myth is the myth that holds women responsible for the sins of the flesh and for tempting men, revealing that the purpose of the myth is to represent women according to patriarchy’s needs, and in contradistinction to whatever man considers himself to be (Elizabeth

Fallaize 90). Additionally, Shakespeare and Soyinka's construction of beautiful and captivating women as femme fatales in the texts under investigation draws attention to the similarities and differences in cultures of Europe and Africa and thus reflects the inherited traditions, warped perceptions and prejudices of their patriarchal societies.

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